

Thermodynamic parameters of micellization and transfer of amino acids from water to aqueous linear alkyl benzene sulphonate

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Abstract : The solution properties of linear alkyl benzene sulphonate (LABS) in water in presence of amino acids have been investigated conductometrically. The critical aggregation concentration (cac) and critical saturation concentration (csc) were determined. It has been observed that at low concentration of surfactant amino acids interact with hydrophilic head group of surfactant molecules and form molecular aggregate/micelle like structure.

Keywords : cac, csc, cmc, gsp, surfactant, micelle, micellization, conductance, linear alkyl benzene sulphonate. LABS.

Introduction

The effect of additives on properties of surfactant in aqueous solution has been a subject of great significance in a variety of industrial and technological processes¹. The size and structure of ionic micelles in presence of additives have been extensively investigated in the last decade². The solvent characteristics like dielectric constant, viscosity, density, hydrogen bond formation capacity and degree of ionization produce a change in the process of micellization in presence of additives. Hence it is difficult to generalize the effect of additives on micellar properties of surfactant in a solvent. The additives may have polar, non-polar or ionic characteristics depending on their structures. In aqueous solution, the amino acids have been reported to be strong structure breakers due to Zwitter ionic nature³. In continuation of our work on micellization of LABS⁴, we report here, the micellization of LABS in aqueous solution of glycine along with thermodynamic parameters.

Results and discussion

Keeping the concentration of glycine constant in aqueous solution, the concentration of LABS is varied and the values of specific conductance observed are given in Table 1. This variation of specific conductance with

concentration was studied by plotting a graph and the representative plot is presented in Fig. 1. In such type of plot there are two break points, the first break point corresponds to the value 14% greater than the critical micelle concentration (cmc) that is $0.0012 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of LABS in water⁵. The further addition of LABS showed a second break point at concentration $0.0035 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ in aqueous solutions of glycine. Above this concentration an increase in specific conductance is observed with the increase in concentration of LABS. In aqueous solution these plots give single break point, which corresponds to the critical micelle concentration (cmc) value of the surfactant. In presence of glycine a different trend in plot was observed. From 0.0002 to $0.0075 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of LABS these break points were independent of glycine in the concentration range 0.02 to 0.04 mol dm^{-3} . The values of break point is decreased from 0.003 to $0.0015 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and 0.0035 to $0.0025 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and remained constant in the same concentration range of LABS. In order to ascertain these specific regions of concentration, the molecular conductance λ of surfactant solution were calculated for each concentration. The plot of molecular conductance versus square root of concentration (c)^{1/2} also indicates the inflection in the curve at the same

Table 1. Variation of specific conductance of LABS with different concentration of glycine

Sl. no.	10 ³ [LABS] (mol dm ⁻³)	Temp. (K)	Specific conductance in ms at					
			0.02 mol dm ⁻³ of glycine	0.04 mol dm ⁻³ of glycine	0.08 mol dm ⁻³ of glycine	0.12 mol dm ⁻³ of glycine	0.16 mol dm ⁻³ of glycine	0.20 mol dm ⁻³ of glycine
1.	0.2	301	0.034	0.021	0.019	0.022	0.024	0.025
		311	0.031	0.029	0.019	0.035	0.032	0.030
2.	0.8	301	0.148	0.120	0.119	0.098	0.096	0.094
		311	0.177	0.157	0.134	0.147	0.124	0.120
3.	1.0	301	0.193	0.149	0.161	0.124	0.120	0.115
		311	0.226	0.204	0.166	0.189	0.152	0.152
4.	1.5	301	0.288	0.228	0.140	0.165	0.175	0.168
		311	0.342	0.300	0.251	0.257	0.229	0.226
5.	2.5	301	0.450	0.355	0.274	0.199	0.229	0.218
		311	0.528	0.465	0.317	0.315	0.283	0.283
6.	3.0	301	0.522	0.422	0.327	0.278	0.271	0.266
		311	0.619	0.541	0.381	0.408	0.334	0.333
7.	3.5	301	0.484	0.413	0.340	0.333	0.311	0.307
		311	0.614	0.534	0.437	0.473	0.383	0.384
8.	4.5	301	0.659	0.541	0.491	0.413	0.417	0.403
		311	0.797	0.705	0.571	0.600	0.503	0.503
9.	5.5	301	0.846	0.646	0.607	0.507	0.516	0.492
		311	0.867	0.872	0.700	0.745	0.622	0.612
10.	6.5	301	0.975	0.773	0.725	0.589	0.605	0.579
		311	1.200	1.000	0.833	0.923	0.724	0.728
11.	7.5	301	1.150	0.878	0.850	0.698	0.698	0.663
		311	1.400	1.170	0.970	1.060	0.837	0.822

Fig. 1. Plot for specific conductance versus [LABS] for 0.02 and 0.04 mol dm⁻³ glycine at 301 K.

concentration region of LABS. The representative plots of molecular conductance λ versus $(c)^{1/2}$ are shown in Fig. 2.

The cmc, however, cannot be determined by this plot but the concave nature of these plots in lower concentration indicates that the surfactant behave as weak electrolytes in lower concentration region. The first break point indicates the critical aggregation concentration, cac,

of glycine surfactant, where the formation of aggregates takes place in the presence of glycine. The addition of glycine have shown a rise in critical micelle concentration values of LABS which is of the same nature as observed in case of an ionic surfactant at sodium lauryl sulphate² whereas the second break point observed in the conductance versus concentration plot is of the same nature as reported in case of polymer surfactant complex formation⁶. In this report this point is defined as cmc of polymer surfactant complex or polymer saturation point in aqueous system. The behavior of LABS micelle in presence of glycine in aqueous solution is somewhat similar to the observed behavior in presence of polymer. In this case this point can be taken as glycine saturation point (gsp). At each concentration of glycine the values obtained for gsp and cac are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Values of gsp, cac and binding capacities of glycine-LABS complex/aggregates

Sl. no.	Glycine (mol dm ⁻³)	gsp (mmol)	cac (mmol)	Binding capacity (mmol LABS/mol glycine)	Degree of ionization (α)	
					301 K	311 K
1.	0.02	3.5	3.0	25.0	0.947	0.951
2.	0.04	3.5	3.0	12.5	0.823	0.872
3.	0.08	2.5	1.5	12.5	0.672	0.733
4.	0.12	2.5	1.5	8.3	0.858	0.849
5.	0.16	2.5	1.5	6.2	0.818	0.739
6.	0.20	2.5	1.5	5.0	0.815	0.730

Fig. 2. Plot for molar conductance versus [LABS]^{1/2} for 0.02 and 0.04 mol dm⁻³ glycine.

The micellization of LABS under the experimental conditions can be explained by the following consideration :

(i) Glycine behaves as weak electrolyte as shown by molecular conductance at lower concentration in aqueous micellar solution of LABS. The plot between molecular conductance and square root of concentration of surfactant, as shown in Fig. 2, supports the fact that the glycine and LABS are weak electrolyte in lower concentration region of LABS. Glycine can form zwitter ion near pH 6.0.

(ii) In the study the glycine saturation point and critical aggregate concentration were obtained at 0.0035 mol dm⁻³

and 0.03 mol dm⁻³ respectively. This concentration region depends upon the concentration of glycine. Above a higher concentration of 0.08 mol dm⁻³ of glycine this concentration region is shifted towards lower concentration region from 0.0025 mol dm⁻³ to 0.0015 mol dm⁻³. These concentration regions were independent of temperature. The presence of this concentration region is only possible when there is a dynamic equilibrium between transient micellar structure and glycine molecule.

(iii) The glycine molecule may exist in a polar or partially ionic form, which can establish interaction with

Fig. 3. Plot for 0.02 mol dm⁻³ alanine and valine.

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters of glycine-LABS system at csc

Sl. no.	Glycine (mol dm ⁻³)	-ΔG ⁰ _{mic} (kJ mol ⁻¹)		ΔS ⁰ _{mic} (kJ K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH ⁰ _{mic} (kJ mol ⁻¹)	
		301 K	311 K		301 K	311 K
1.	0.02	25.47	26.22	0.075	-2.89	-2.89
2.	0.04	28.47	28.19	-0.028	-36.89	-36.89
3.	0.08	33.23	32.76	-0.047	-47.37	-47.37
4.	0.12	28.57	29.76	0.119	7.24	7.24
5.	0.16	29.57	32.59	0.302	61.33	61.33
6.	0.2	29.64	32.82	0.318	66.07	66.07

surfactant molecule. This interaction corresponds to the first break point in concentration versus specific conductance graph and can be defined as $cmc1$ or critical aggregation concentration, cac , of glycine-LABS complex/aggregate.

(iv) The $cmc2$ or critical saturation concentration, csc corresponds to the second break point in specific conductance and concentration plot. Further addition of LABS beyond this point, the additional glycine molecules around the aggregates create the charged structure responsible for the repulsion between micelle and glycine molecules. In this region the micellar form of LABS is dominant having attractive/repulsive nature with positive or negative charge end of glycine molecule in dynamic equilibrium.

(v) The value of cac was higher from cmc of LABS in aqueous solution. It can be explained in terms of hydrogen bond formation ability of glycine molecules, which leads to weak contribution to the hydrophobic interaction responsible for the formation of micelles. The assumption is justified with the results that the glycine behaves as structure breaker in aqueous solution⁷.

(vi) In the aqueous solution of glycine the polar and non-polar part of surfactant monomers are involved in non-covalent interactions different in nature and independently influenced due to the presence of zwitter ion in contact with water. In aqueous solution of glycine the surfactant exists in monomeric form at lower concentration. At critical aggregation concentration, cac , the self-interaction of both surfactant and water molecule cannot be compensated by their mutual interactions, the surfactant monomer tends to associate in a regular pattern forming glycine surfactant aggregates or micelle.

In order to verify the specific effect of amino acids on micellization of LABS in aqueous solutions L-alanine and valine having formula $CH_3CH(NH_2)COOH$ and $(CH_3)_2CHCH(NH_2)COOH$ respectively were used in place of glycine. For these amino acids the values of cac (critical aggregation concentration) and csc (critical saturation concentration) were $0.003 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $0.0035 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Fig. 4. Variation of specific conductance with concentration of glycine for [LABS]: (a) $0.0008 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (b) $0.0015 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (c) $0.0025 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (d) $0.0045 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

for alanine and $0.002 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $0.003 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ for valine at 301 K in 0.02 mol dm^{-3} aqueous solution of amino acids. The respective plots for both the amino acids between specific conductance and concentration of LABS are given in Fig. 3.

The other concentrations of these amino acids were not studied because there is a similarity in behavior with glycine. It is clear from Fig. 3 that the cac and csc of alanine and glycine are same whereas these values are shifted towards lower concentration of LABS. It can be concluded that the carboxylic group is responsible for interaction with surfactant molecule. In case of valine the long tail of the amino acid facilitate the aggregation process. The oxygen atom of carboxylic group of amino acid molecule with partially negative charge may interact with surfactant molecule. It is obvious that the specific conductance of aqueous LABS solution either increases or decreases in presence of amino acid with increasing concentration. The conclusion drawn in the study was further tested from the plots between specific conductance and concentration of amino acid, at different constant concentration of LABS. These plots are represented in Fig. 4. All these plots have similar nature in which the value of specific conductance is decreasing with the increasing concentration of amino acid at lower concentration whereas the value of specific conductance at higher concentration region of amino acid has slightly increased constant values. The decrease in specific conductance is only possible when the amino acid and surfactant molecules are forming a neutral aggregate by mutual ionic interactions.

Fig. 5. Enthalpy versus entropy.

Thermodynamic quantities of micellization :

In the study it has been concluded that micelles/micellar aggregates are formed between glycine and monomeric surfactant. This conclusion is based on the values of c_{ac} and c_{sc} , which were independent of temperature. Thermodynamic quantities provide more information about the interaction between surfactant and glycine molecules and formation of micellar aggregate. At c_{ac} the degree of ionization (α) value of glycine-LABS complex/aggregates were computed from slopes of conductance-concentration plots below c_{ac} and above c_{ac} . These values are given in Table 2. The values of α and c_{ac} were used to calculate the free energy of micellization ΔG_{mic}^0 at c_{ac} . The eq. (1) which is applicable to ionic surfactant⁸ was used to calculate ΔG_{mic}^0 .

$$\Delta G_{mic}^0 = (2 - \alpha) RT \ln c_{sc} \quad (1)$$

where c_{sc} is in mol fraction scale. In the above relation ΔG_{mic}^0 at c_{sc} is expressed in per monomer unit by conceptual approximation. In pseudo-phase model the monomer concentration at c_{sc} remains non variant, with increasing surfactant concentration above c_{sc} micelles are only formed. Further standard entropy of micellization ΔS_{mic}^0 and enthalpy of micellization ΔH_{mic}^0 were calculated using the eqs. (2) and (3) as used in case of mixed solvent⁹.

$$\Delta S_{mic}^0 = \delta(\Delta G_{mic}^0)/\delta T \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta H_{mic}^0 = \Delta G_{mic}^0 + T\Delta S_{mic}^0 \quad (3)$$

The thermodynamic quantities thus calculated at different concentration of glycine are recorded in Table 3. A perusal of Table 3 shows ΔG_{mic}^0 for all concentration of glycine are negative and these values increase (become more negative) with increase in concentration of glycine upto 0.08 mol dm^{-3} . This confirms that the strong interaction between LABS monomer and glycine molecule results in the formation of micelles/aggregates in this concentration region. In the same concentration region at high temperature these interaction are less effective due to the increase in thermal energy. At higher concentration of glycine from 0.12 mol dm^{-3} to 0.20 mol dm^{-3} the micellization was feasible. The enthalpy of micellization values are negative in the lower concentration region of glycine, whereas at higher concentration these values are positive due to endothermic nature. The ΔS_{mic}^0 values remain constant with increase in temperature for each concentration of glycine. This indicates that glycine surfactant are more favoured by entropy change. At lower concentration the entropy value is nearly zero which also confirms the equilibrium between glycine and surfactant molecule. For this concentration region the plot between enthalpy versus entropy change was obtained. The nature of the plot was linear as represented in Fig. 5.

This plot also indicates that the glycine surfactant interaction is favoured only by entropy change as the value of ΔH_{mic}^0 becomes zero at entropy value $0.08 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. Such enthalpy entropy compensation effect was reported for many physico chemical processes¹⁰. The standard free energy of transfer was calculated from the eq. (4) as reported for micelle formation in mixed solvent¹¹.

$$\Delta G_{tr}^0 = (2 - \alpha) RT \ln [c_{mc}/c_{ac}] + (2 - \alpha) RT \ln [f_0/f] \quad (4)$$

where c_{mc} is for pure water, c_{ac} is c_{mc} in glycine solution, f_0 is the activity of surfactant in water and f is the activity in presence of glycine.

For lower concentration range of glycine the value of c_{ac} is $0.003 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and for higher concentration range the value of c_{ac} is $0.0015 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. These values

are independent of temperature. When f_0/f is taken equal to unity, the standard free energy of transfer at lower concentration, 0.02 mol dm^{-3} of glycine was -2.41 kJ at 301 K . At higher concentration of glycine (0.12 mol dm^{-3}), the ΔG_{tr}^0 was -0.64 kJ at 301 K . For both the concentration the cmc value of LABS in pure water $0.0012 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ was used as reported in literature⁶. The negative value indicates the feasibility of transfer of LABS from pure water to glycine rich water phase. This confirm again the results concluded in the study. The results of thermodynamic parameters observed in viscometric and volumetric studies¹² also support the conclusion of this study. At csc the adsorption at charged sites of glycine molecule by LABS monomer shows the formation of independent micelle after saturation point.

Conclusion :

The micellization of LABS in presence of aqueous glycine solutions has shown that the glycine and surfactant behave as weak electrolyte. The free energy of micellization in the study has the same trend as reported for non ionic surfactant in glucose solution². At lower concentration of glycine it was observed that the formation of glycine-LABS aggregate/micelle takes place which was also justified by the data of binding capacities at different concentration. In this study it has been observed¹³ that at low concentration of surfactant, amino acids are still in the water phase and mainly interact with hydrophilic head groups of surfactant molecule in case of cationic surfactant which is in good agreement with the conclusion drawn in the study. At higher concentration of LABS the interaction with glycine molecule is decreased and further increase in concentration correspond to a saturation point beyond which micellization of surfactant followed a regular trend of post micellization like in water. Higher concentration of glycine have small value of standard free energy of transfer, which indicates the non feasibility of transfer of LABS from pure water to glycine rich water phase. This study may be useful for the interpretation of kinetic data in the oxidation of amino acids in presence of LABS in aqueous solution, which is the objective of the study.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

De-ionized water twice distilled was used in all the studies. The specific conductance of the water prepared for the present study was of the order of $<2 \times 10 \Omega \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The LABS used in the study were obtained in the laboratory by sulphonation of linear alkyl benzenes (IPCL, $C_{10} = 14$, $C_{11} = 31$, $C_{12} = 37$, $C_{13} = 16$ and $C_{14} = 1\%$) having an average molecular weight of 343. Surface tension measurements were made on an aqueous solution of LABS prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed sample in distilled water. No surface tension minima were found which implies that no surface-active impurities exist in the studied LABS samples. The techniques employed for test of impurities was same as reported in literature². The solutions of glycine (Loba), alanine (Merck) and valine (Cisco) were prepared by dissolving the calculated amount in distilled water.

Conductance measurements :

Conductance measurement were carried out on a digital conductivity meter (Systronics type 306) with a sensitivity of 0.1% and a dipping type conductivity cell with a platinum electrode of cell constant 1.0. All the measurements were made at constant temperature using thermostatically controlled water bath (Tanco, Kanpur) capable of maintaining the temperature constant to $\pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

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Kandpal *et al.* : Thermodynamic parameters of micellization and transfer of amino acids from water *etc.*

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